

New Complexes of Nickel (II) Using 4-Hydroxy-2-Oxo-2H-Chromene-3-Carboxamide as Ligand

Dije Dehari, Ahmed Jashari, Shefket Dehari, Agim Shabani

Abstract—New complexes of nickel (II) have been synthesized in the reaction mixture of nickel (II) acetate and 4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide. Bis(4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamidato-O,O)nickel (II) and diaquabis(4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamidato-O,O)nickel (II) were characterized by elemental analysis, IR spectroscopy and ESI mass spectrometry. Elemental analysis and mass spectrometry data of the complexes suggests the stoichiometry of 1:2 (metal-ligand).

Keywords—Nickel complexes, 4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide, IR spectroscopy, mass spectrometry.

I. INTRODUCTION

COUMARIN is a structural unit of many natural and synthetic compounds which endows them with a wide range of physiological and pharmacological activities as antibacterial [2], [3], antiviral [4], [5], bactericidal [6], fungicidal [7], anti-inflammatory [8], and anticoagulants [9]. The interest has grown up when remarkable anticancer [10]–[13] and lately anti-HIV [14], [15] activities of some coumarins were confirmed. Especially the coumarin derivative 4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide (1) attracted our attention as potentially very active compound in live cells, because of the functional groups connected to each other in the six-member pyranon system. Furthermore, those are very polar groups, (keto, hydroxy and amido) which are able to create interactions (as hydrogen bond for example) with the large biomolecules as guest-host systems. Also, the geometric position of those groups is perfect to embrace metal cations. Theoretically, its deprotonated species especially should show pronounced ability for complexation. Namely, this compound can serve as a versatile polyfunctional ligand being included as:

- a) an ion
- b) a ligand coordinated through:
 - the nitrogen atom and deprotonated hydroxyl group
 - the carbonyl oxygen atom from the amido group and deprotonated hydroxyl group,
 - the nitrogen atom and the carbonyl oxygen atom from the pyranon ring
 - the carbonyl oxygen atom from the amido group and the

Dije Dehari, Ahmed Jashari, Shefket Dehari, and Agim Shabani are with the State University of Tetovo, Faculty of Mathematical and Natural Sciences, Department of Chemistry, 1200 Tetovo, Macedonia (tel: +38971797661; e-mail: dije.dehari@yahoo.com).

- carbonyl oxygen atom from the pyranon ring
- c) a neutral molecule

Many researchers synthesized the complexes of transition metals with coumarin derivatives because these complexes that contain coumarin as a ligand show anticoagulant properties [16], [17] and antitumor activity [18], [19]. Kostova et al. have shown the cytotoxic potential of coumarins complexed with cerium, lanthanum, zirconium and neodymium [20]–[22].

In this work we have shown the synthesis of nickel complexes with 4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide as ligand using triethylamine for the deprotonation of hydroxyl group in C-4 position.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Melting points were determined on a Reichert heating plate and are uncorrected. C, H elemental analysis was carried out with Coleman Model 33. N elemental analysis was carried out by the Dumas method. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 400 MHz instrument using DMSO- d_6 as solvent and tetramethylsilane as internal standard. Infrared spectra (KBr pellets) were measured on a Perkin-Elmer System 2000 FT IR. ESI-tof mass spectra were measured using an LCT mass spectrometer (Waters) equipped with a lockspray dual-electrospray ion source combined with Waters alliance 2695 HPLC unit.

All the reagents and solvents were obtained from commercial sources and were used without further purification.

A. Preparation of Ligand

10g (60mmol) of 4-hydroxycoumarin were poured in round-bottom flask and 5g (80mmol) of urea were added. The flask was stopped with glass stopper and the compounds were mixed well. Afterwards, the flask was mounted on the vertical condenser which was previously inducted in the domestic microwave oven through the manually madden hole. The power was set to 850W and the timer to 5min. After this time the mixture was left to cold and then it was dissolved in worm ethanol. After crystallization white needles of the pure product were formed. Anal. Calc. for $C_{10}H_7NO_4$: C 58.54%; H 3.44%; N 6.83%, found: C 58.02%, H 3.12%, N 6.16%. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3353 (vasNH), 3201 (vsNH), 3500-3100 (vOH – overwrite), 1702 (vC=O, pyr), 1643 (vC=O, amide). 1H -NMR (δ , ppm, Fig. 3): 7.90 (s, 1H, NH_2), 7.63 (s, 1H, NH_2), 6.73 (dd, 1H, Ar), 6.57 (td, 1H, Ar) and 6.21 (m, 2H, Ar). ESI-MS

m/z 206.0 (M+H⁺).

B. Preparation of Ni Complex (1a)

124mg (0.5mmol) of Ni(OAc)₂ x 4H₂O were measured and dissolved in 15ml dried methanol in room temperature. Also, 1mmol (205mg) of the ligand (1) were measured and dissolved in 15ml dried methanol and 0.2ml triethylamine were added in room temperature. The solution of the ligand was added in the nickel solution and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 25min at 50°C. The light green nickel complex precipitated, filtered and washed with ethanol and diethyleter.

Anal. calc. for C₂₀H₁₂N₂NiO₈: C, 51.44; H, 2.59; N, 6.00; Found: C, 50.92; H, 2.24; N, 5.67. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3298, 1695, 1622, 1505, 1199, 1039, 762, 674. ESI-MS (m/z) 467.0 (M+H⁺); Mp: 220°C (decomp).

C. Preparation of Ni Complex (1b)

124mg (0.5mmol) of Ni(OAc)₂ x 4H₂O were measured and dissolved in 15ml methanol + 5ml H₂O in room temperature. Also, 1mmol (205mg) of the ligand (1) were measured and dissolved in 15ml methanol and 0.2ml triethylamine were added in room temperature. The solution of the ligand was added in the nickel solution and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 20min at 40°C. The greenish nickel complex precipitated, filtered and washed with ethanol and diethyleter.

Anal. calc. for C₂₀H₁₆N₂NiO₁₀: C, 47.75; H, 3.21; N, 5.57; Found: C, 46.92; H, 3.14; N, 5.47. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3417, 1694, 1620, 1559, 1490, 1476, 767, 679. ESI-MS m/z 502.02 (M+H⁺); Mp: 215°C (decomp).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the pre-search of the literature poor information was found for the compound 1. It was found that it was synthesized by Scarborough and Gould [1] in 1961, using direct method of melting 4-hydroxycoumarin with urea according to the reaction gave in the Fig. 1. However, this procedure was repeated over and over and the compound was obtained but in very moderate yields (ca. 25%). On the other hand, we attempt to melt this mixture using microwave irradiation. In this case, when the mixture was melted in domestic microwave oven, on 850 W for 3-5 minutes, the result was slightly better obtaining 30-35% yield.

Fig. 1 Synthesis of the 4-Hydroxy-2-Oxo-2H-Chromene-3Carboxamide (1)

A. Elemental Analysis

The elemental analysis data match very well with those calculated and they show that nickel is coordinated with ligand in 1:2 ratio.

B. IR Spectra

On the measured IR spectra of ligand (1) it can be noticed that two bands are present on 3353 and 3201cm⁻¹ from the antisymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the NH₂ groups [23]. Also two C=O vibrational bands on 1702 and 1643cm⁻¹, one from the carbonyl group attached on the pyrane ring and the other from the amide group [24]. The hydroxyl group shows at 3440cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 IR spectrum of ligand (1)

The complex (1a) shows a band of amino groups at 3298cm⁻¹. The C=O bands of amido groups appear at the 1622cm⁻¹ which shows that the ligand is coordinated with nickel (II) through carbonyl groups and deprotonated phenolic groups. The free carbonyl groups of piranon ring appear at 1695cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3 ¹H-NMR spectrum of ligand (1)

The complex (1b) shows a broad band of hydroxyl groups at 3600-3300cm⁻¹ with maximum absorption in the 3417cm⁻¹. These bands show the coordinated water molecules to the Ni (II) ion in the complex. The C=O bands of amido groups appear at the 1620cm⁻¹ which also shows that the ligand is coordinated with nickel (II) through carbonyl groups and deprotonated phenolic groups. The free carbonyl groups of piranon ring appear at 1694cm⁻¹ (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 IR spectrum of Ni complex (1a)

Fig. 5 IR spectrum of Ni complex (1b)

C. Mass Spectra

The m/z value of ligand (**1**) confirms the structure as shown in Fig. 1. The m/z values of complexes prove that complexes were formed in the above mentioned ratio. The experimental values of ESI-MS are almost the same with theoretically

calculated (Table I). The mass spectrums of complexes (**1a**) and (**1b**) are shown in Figs. 7 and 8.

TABLE I
 MASS SPECTERS OF LIGAND AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	m/z Calc. (M)	m/z Found
$C_{10}H_7NO_4$ (1)	205.04	206.0(M + H ⁺)
$C_{20}H_{12}N_2NiO_8$ (1a)	465.99	467.0(M + H ⁺)
$C_{20}H_{16}N_2NiO_{10}$ (1b)	502.02	500.9(M - H ⁺)

(1a)

(1b)

Fig. 6 Suggested structures of Ni complexes

Fig. 7 Mass spectrum of Ni complex (1a)

Fig. 8 Mass spectrum of Ni complex (**1b**)

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